

DIFFICULTIES IN LEARNING IELTS

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Abstract: Relevance and statement of the problem. Reform of the education system as a whole and transformations in higher education are very closely related to the modifications that occur in the social life of the country, since they directly reflect the trends in the development of society.

Keywords: Modernization, IELTS, module, Academic Reading, General Training Reading, intensive reading.

A modern country that has entered the international educational space is characterized by a desire to improve the education system and adapt the national characteristics of higher education to international requirements and educational standards.

The modernization of the education system is accompanied by significant changes in pedagogical theory and organization of the educational process, aimed at introducing innovative approaches to teaching, which provide the opportunity to merge the Uzbek education system with international educational standards on the terms of full-fledged relevant partnership and cooperation.

The innovation of the education system is reflected in the integral components of the learning process: curricula, teaching technologies and the teaching process itself.

In this regard, it is advisable to familiarize yourself with the format of international English language exams International English Language Testing System (IELTS), highlight its features, and also systematize possible techniques and exercises for its successful completion.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the main methods and techniques for improving the quality of reading in English, as well as to develop recommendations for preparing for the IELTS exam in the "Reading" module.

As you know, there is a system of international exams aimed at proving the knowledge of the English language necessary to achieve the intended educational goal. The variability of examination formats provides for the differentiation of the purpose and degree of understanding of the English language, as well as the areas of its application.

It should be noted that in the Russian Federation, among the international exams, the most famous are the classical English (Cambridge) exams, which are focused on the British version of the English language, as well as the international exam IELTS (International English Language Testing System - an international testing system for English language).

IELTS is a test for those who intend to study or practice in an English-speaking environment; it makes it possible to determine the degree of English proficiency of people who are not native speakers. IELTS is recognized by most British, Australian, Canadian, and New Zealand educational institutions. The IELTS result is recognized in virtually all countries of the world (including the UK and the USA) [6].

The second most numbered IELTS module is “Reading” and consists of 3 sections and 40 questions. The duration of testing is no more than 60 minutes.

The subject is required to read the text and answer 40 questions that contain certain clarifications regarding the text read. Academic and General formats contain different texts in this module.

Academic Reading format contains three parts. The total volume of texts in this format is 2000-2750 words. According to the developers of the test, texts for the academic format are taken from newspapers, books and magazines and correspond to the general cultural training of the test takers, that is, they do not contain highly specific professional information.

The general format (General Training Reading) consists of three texts on general topics with a total volume of 2000-2500 words, which can be taken from newspapers, magazines, advertisements, brochures, official documents.

Next, we will analyze possible methods and exercises that can facilitate the process of preparing for IELTS testing in the Reading module.

In the process of preparing for the IELTS exam in the Reading module, a necessary condition is the development of reading skills, taking into account the importance of:

- a) complete understanding of the content of easy texts;
- b) training skills in understanding the main content of texts of various genres that are complex in content and structure: popular science, socio-political and artistic.

Let's consider two basic methodologies for developing reading skills:

1. Introductory (search) reading with understanding of the main content of the text (Scanning reading and Skimming reading).

Skimming reading refers to reading to determine the main idea, theme, problem, or purpose of a text. The task of Scanning reading is to find specific information, for example, determine where an event occurs, find names, dates, find synonyms.

Consequently, in the process of introductory reading the following goals are pursued:

- determination of the topic that is covered in the text, determination of the problems discussed in the text, as well as determination of specific information about this problem;
- highlighting the main idea;
- selection of basic facts, omitting secondary ones;
- identification of the author's position.

Students must understand the content of the text and comprehend the information received. Students should be oriented to the fact that, as a rule, the main semantic load in the text is carried by the first paragraph (introduction), as well as the beginning and ending sentences of each paragraph.

Working with the text in the introductory reading mode involves fluent reading for 3-4 minutes to obtain basic information.

Before working on a new text, the teacher must direct students' attention to reading and understanding the text. It names the problem/field of science addressed in the text. You can ask students what they know about this problem and how they feel about it.

At the preparatory stage of working with the text, it is necessary to perform pre-text exercises in order to remove some of the language and semantic difficulties of the text. R.P. Milrud gives an example of such exercises:

- practicing the pronunciation of geographical names, names, as well as some words. Here you can add words that students traditionally make mistakes in pronunciation, for example: infinite, inventory, consequences, purchasing, etc.
- work with individual words related to the potential vocabulary: international, derivative, complex. Students must guess the meaning of these words and give their translation options.
- practicing complex grammatical structures through their analysis and translation.

One of the important types of work at the pre-text stage is predicting both the content of the text and the forms of words. The following tasks are aimed at predicting content:

- determining the main theme/thought of the text by title and subtitle (if any);
- determination of the main idea of the text and the author's attitude towards the problem raised in the first and last paragraphs of the text;
- choosing the main topic of the text from a number of proposed topics after reading the title of the text.

Such exercises are very important for practicing exam types such as fill-in-the-blank tables, diagrams, summaries, and sentence completion tasks.

Reading a text in order to understand the main content is regulated depending on the volume and complexity of the text. Reading comprehension is monitored by performing post-text exercises:

- selection of headings for paragraphs of text;
- answers to questions on the basic information of the text in the form of short answers, in the form of choosing the correct answer from several proposed answers;
- determining the reliability of the proposed statement of information presented in the text;
- finding specific information.

At this stage, the ability to navigate the text, find units of semantic information is tested, for example, quickly find and read a sentence in which the main characters are named (location, time, characteristics of the characters, causes and consequences of actions, etc.).

Quickly finding the necessary information in a text is facilitated, for example, not by reading, but by searching, for which the reverse scanning technique is used, when the text is viewed not as in traditional reading from left to right and top to bottom, but from bottom to top and right to left. This allows you to avoid involuntary reading of words and helps to isolate the necessary information.

As a rule, all study guides for preparing for the IELTS exam offer recommendations on how to complete a particular task in the exam. The teacher should compile a bank of such recommendations for each assignment. Such information, communicated to students, will help them create their own algorithm for completing each type of task.

At the same time, it is important to encourage students to increase their reading speed through exercises such as:

- reading a text/passage of text over a certain period of time. For this type of exercise, it is necessary to select texts or passages of the same length and difficulty and gradually reduce the reading time;
- reading sentences with gradually increasing elements over the same period of time;
- reading the text and quickly finding an answer to the teacher's question;

- restoration of “blurry” text.
2. Reading with full comprehension of the text (intensive reading).

It should be noted that this type of reading is not used in the IELTS exam, but work on this type of reading is necessary at the preparation stage, since it is this type of reading that serves as the basis for replenishing the active and passive vocabulary of readers, as well as mastering grammatical structures and methods of transmitting information in the text.

This type of reading requires a lot of time and effort on the part of students to master it in full.

Before reading a text, it is necessary to set various tasks for students in order to gradually familiarize them with the specifics of intensive reading and develop in them the skills necessary to successfully pass the IELTS exam: highlighting the main idea; summarizing what you read; finding answers to the questions asked; reading a diagram or depicting what has been read schematically or in the form of a drawing.

Preparation for the IELTS exam in the Reading module should be considered as the basis for comprehensive preparation for modules such as Speaking, Writing, and also, first of all, as a source of vocabulary replenishment and, in particular, Academic Vocabulary. As practice shows, many words included in the Academic Word List are found in a variety of texts both to prepare for the exam and directly in the exam texts themselves. Therefore, the teacher should not only familiarize students with the Academic Word List, but also work through these words in each type of work on the text. For these purposes, we can recommend the following:

1. Students themselves find words from the Academic Word List in the text, give their definitions, build synonymic and word-formative series and prepare examples with these words.
2. The teacher prepares exercises for practicing these and other words chosen by him to replenish the active vocabulary of students.
3. The teacher gives the following tasks to develop speech skills:
 - convey the main idea of each paragraph of text using words from active vocabulary.
 - prepare a short / detailed retelling of the text using new words / expressions. prepare your story or describe a situation using at least 15 new words / expressions (this is usually homework).

In Part II of the module, students must prepare a 1-2-minute mini-speech on one of the following topics: Describe a happy childhood event. You should say: When it happened; Who was involved; How did you feel at the time. Explain why you remember this particular occasion. Or: Describe your school.

You should say: What the name of your school is; Where it is; What is it like; What impresses you most about this school.

Part III of the Speaking module involves answering more general and abstract questions within 3-4 minutes. Here you can suggest the following questions: What do you think about the problem of violence at school? Should parents teach children not to hit back at bullies?

Work on Part II of the written module of the IELTS exam (essay writing) on the general topic “The youth” should also be carried out taking into account the use of active vocabulary. To write an essay like “The opinion essay,” you can suggest the following topic: It is widely believed that children of different levels of intelligence should be taught together, while others think that more intelligent children should be taught separately. Discuss and present

your own opinion. Give reasons for your answer and include any relevant examples from your own knowledge or experience.

In this article, we looked at the main types of exercises and tasks in English, the purpose of which is to develop reading skills.

During our research, we sought to analyze the features of preparing for the IELTS exam in the Reading module, and the proposed set of exercises will help improve not only reading skills, but also speech skills in preparation for exam modules such as Speaking and Writing

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